

The transformation of an archaeological community and its resulting representations in the context of the co-development of open Archaeological Information Systems

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Abstract

The adoption of Archaeological Information Systems (AIS) evolves according to multiple factors, both human and technical, as well as endogenous and exogenous. In consequence the ever increasing scope of digital tools, which allow for the organization of information in order to understand the transformations of an archaeological site, transforms the organizations that generate or manage these data. The transformations induced by digital methods are carriers of an antagonism between continuity and discontinuity, which leads to constant reorganization. At the same time online collaboration and

design (centered on and with the user) allow for open access to data, to code and to make the design process accessible to the greatest number. In this spirit, archaeology seeks interoperability and reusability (e.g. FAIR principles, LOUD data), which in return, leads to the emergence of new organizations of information, as for example, the definition of criteria for interoperability, data models dedicated to data exchange (e.g. CIDOC CRM), dissemination platforms, the scripting of treatments in order to make these reproducible, or the sharing of terminologies. Hereby interoperability takes on a dual sense: An “internal interoperability”, encompassing the current process of retrieving data as it is stored in the primary recording system of the excavation and their transformation for their traditional publication or storage in digital repositories, and an “external interoperability”, encompassing the effort of linking these "final" data with already existing data in order to facilitate exploitation by any kind of future research. In this contribution we present an approach to study the emergence of the relationship between the organization of information and the transformation of the organization. The study is conducted in view of the SIAMOIS project (“Mutualized and Open Archaeological Information System based on Semantic Intelligence”) which has the objective to master these relationships in a collaborative context.

In order to analyze these transformations, we propose a conceptualized analysis model, formalized in the T!O (Transformation, Information, Organization) framework. This framework takes seriously the principle of “Tertium non datur” in classical logic by using a relational approach. In this way the differences expressed within the conventional binary logic are not understood as conflicting opposites, but as a source for a dynamic equilibrium where the actualization of one state is simultaneous with the potentialization of the other. Thereby a formalized representation of the organization of an archaeological community is produced and the processes constituting the generation of knowledge are brought into view and can become the object of particular attention.

As a use case, the paper analyzes the production of archaeological knowledge by modeling excavation processes and the establishment of discourse based on typologies which are employed in publications, in order to show how the T!O framework allows for reflecting on institutional processes at the same time as it indicates the necessary parameters to organize and record archaeological data. Modeling these processes brings “silences” in the archeological data to the fore, which are either generally left unconsidered as implicit knowledge, or at least problematized when the attempt is made to transform the same knowledge by way of ontologies. Our approach shows that only magnifying the individual processes of knowledge production in a research project ultimately allows for those “shared conceptualizations” that are sought when aligning AIS and ontologies under the objective of publishing archaeological data.

Keywords: archaeological information system, interoperability, knowledge production, organizational modeling, ontology, thesaurus

Introduction

Archeology collects, identifies, describes and quantifies, in order to understand and explain ancient material realities and connections among them - in other words, Archaeology writes a rational history of human societies based on the traces they leave behind. Archaeological research programs are held to report all of these stages when publishing the results of this process. The completeness of the transmitted information to the scientific community is essential as it supports the argumentation within the scientific discourse by accounting for the hypotheses formulated based on the observed remains and further knowledge used, to generate a conclusive interpretation. Actualizations of the discourse are part of a continuous process, which requires recurrent publication.

Present approaches to publishing archaeological knowledge leave considerable parts of this process untraceable. In the present paper we identify three primary processes with an increased need for transparency. On the one hand we need to deal with an “internal interoperability”, encompassing the current process of retrieving data as it is stored in the primary recording system of the excavation and their transformation with a view to their traditional publication or storage in digital repositories. On the other hand “external interoperabilities”, encompass the effort of linking these “final” data with already existing data in order to facilitate exploitation by any kind of future research, including interests in other regions, pertaining to other periods, conducted by archaeologists using other methodologies or even interdisciplinary research. While these processes are already managed in databases at present, albeit not necessarily distinguished there, a third aspect is consistently missing from archaeological recording systems: the contextual information containing the who-does-what, why and how of research.

As we will show, the two interoperabilities are thoroughly entwined, as decisions made during the conceptualization of a recording system require ontological decisions right from the onset and on the same level as the well-known reflections to further external interoperability of data by using ontologies. The similarity between the initial and the ultimate stage of ontological reflection can be seen as one of the main reasons why these two processes are not distinguished in recording systems. Ultimately it is this third aspect, the in-depth investigation of the specific archaeological processes within individual projects, which will allow for resolving issues of interoperability.

Retrotheorization and Shared Conceptualization

In order to understand the intricate relationship of internal and external interoperability, a brief look into the history of archaeological information systems is revealing. Even before the invention of the personal computer, excavation data had been integrated in mainframe computers by way of databases which were mostly developed either by computer scientists with an affinity to archaeology, or - and that was surprisingly often the case - archaeologists themselves invested their time in programming. In consequence, the first knowledge systems were brought to use in the 1970s and while these systems were initially dedicated to singular excavation projects, later systems like Plutarch (“Program Library Useful To ARChaeologists” - see Wilcock 1974) or Syslat (Roure et al. 2021) were conceived for implementation on multiple sites.

The logical architecture of these systems engaged the technology available at the time and were mostly implemented as hierarchical and then increasingly as relational databases. Following the advancement

of AI during the 1970s, archaeologists also began developing expert systems, which required the modeling of conceptual schema reflecting the field of research in question. While these applications did not yet use ontology as a label, expert systems slowly gave way to the idea of computational ontologies and if in theory not properly formalized, the archaeological knowledge systems in use did very much follow Thomas Gruber's oft-cited definition of ontologies as "formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization" (1995). Although probably reflecting the most common understanding of ontologies, this definition is not the only notion of ontology. As another example, Grenon (et al.) define an ontology as grasping "the entities which exist within a given portion of the world at a given level of generality" (2004). Grenon (et al.) point to the metaphysical problem of ontologies – the question of the relationship between data and the world from which the data is extracted. While Gruber focuses on "collective conceptualization" and the idea that the user group accepts data as adequate (and that each user discusses the relationship between data and reality for themselves), Grenon (et al.) use a definition of ontology in the classical philosophical sense. As Khazraee and Lin (2011) point out, the term "ontology" finds nearly anarchic use today and if before the onset of computer ontologies, the term ontology was primarily understood based on its metaphysical connotation, now and especially with the work of Philippe Descola (2014) and Viveiros DeCastro (2019) ontologies are limited to relativism. This development is parallel with the loss of objectivity in the aftermath of the linguistic turn (Rorty 2002), and subsequent investigations into the modalities of research practices (e.g. Latour/Woolgar 2013, Knorr-Cetina 1999, Latour 1999, Knorr-Cetina 2013, Daston/Galison 2010). Where archaeological theory in the same vein until the 1980s attempted to unify research by implementing models of explanation (for a detailed summary see Salmon 1982 and Salmon 1992) research today seems more driven by the continuous recalibration of theoretical conceptions to determine the validity of a statement.

Independent of the metaphysical status of either approach to ontology, for the present discussion the definition of ontologies as "shared conceptualizations" shall suffice. With this definition ontologies (and other conceptualized knowledge systems) can at least be understood as reflections or even materializations of epistemic cultures (Knorr-Cetina 1999) and as such the interactions of researchers within these cultures can be shown as being in tension with either advancing their research or being constrained by the inherent structures of the systems. On a temporal trajectory, knowledge systems evolve and their positionality changes over time as they are continuously realigned. Just as Neurath's ship (Quine 1960) shows, knowledge is in a constant state of transformation (e.g. CIDOC-CRM is at version 7 now): Neurath describes a vessel which cannot be docked in a harbor and therefore repairs as well as remodeling must be executed while at sea. Similar to the "ship of Theseus," Neurath's ship is a metaphor for the constant endeavor of producing knowledge whilst never being able to start from scratch. In consequence knowledge is always fluid and can only be grasped as perspectival reflections. Without recourse to metaphysics, ontologies are then merely determined by their social context - a group committing to the defining criteria and the interdependencies of the classes and properties constituting them. In order to determine which ontology is most suitable for a given situation or social context, it is necessary to clarify the decision-making processes for each entity structuring the data. Either a group comes to an informed decision to employ a pre-existing ontology, or by establishing their own structure and defining the groups' ideas of how knowledge should be formed in their domain. Unfortunately these considerations are more often than not taken by a very restricted group of a research team (the project director, a database/software developer, sometimes even including field directors and directors of specialist laboratories) and leave the majority of participants to the project outside of that development process. Only in rare cases (e.g. excavations conducted following a

reflexive approach¹) data highlighting the details of the excavation process are recorded. These missing types of data include names of archaeologists beyond those listed as authors of research reports, their specialties, the tools used, the methods implemented, the configuration parameters of the digital recorders – or even more generally the conditions which make the excavation possible, such as its financing, or further circumstantial data. Failing to record these data, makes it difficult to retrace this information when inquiring into the original datasets or attempting to use automatic inferencing on a repository, where an AIS potentially ends up for long-term storage. While some projects take the participants to a project more seriously, collaboration at the moment of initial development of the informational structure is certainly a rare feat.

Considering our initial distinction of internal and external interoperability, the historical sketch of AIS development allows for understanding the similarities between the development of a new recording system and the procedures leading to an appropriate mapping of an existing data structure. In fact, the CIDOC-CRM (Bekiari et al 2021) has not only been used as a reference model for final publications of closed databases, but also as a catalog of guidelines to define the inherent logic for new research projects - e.g. AIR (Derudas et al. 2023), Himat (Hiebel et al. 2014), Arches (Carlisle et al. 2014) or ResearchSpace (Oldman/Tanase 2018). Quite unsurprisingly, the above mentioned deliberations during the development of an AIS and the mapping of data onto an existing ontology concern the definition of appropriate containers for archaeological information as they are conceived by the group constituting a research project. The main difference then is merely the temporal perspective, stressing futurity when arguing that an ontology in question is acceptable as underlying structure of an AIS or underscoring historicity when research data are published and the structures of an ontology and a domain conceptualization are being negotiated. Either an AIS is developed in regard to its theoretical implications, or the potential interoperability of a system with a certain ontology (after having used a recording system for a while), is done by retrotheorization. This again is most often achieved without the developers of the initial conceptualization and especially without the people involved during the actual excavations. The process of transforming data towards interoperability is therefore isolated (truncated) from the process of conceptualization and generation of data at all stages of transformation. Theseus' ship would surely present a dire picture if it was treated like that.

Modeling the organization of knowledge: stratigraphic unit vs. excavation unit

In order to clarify how differences in defining certain classes of data have effects on the interpretation of the resulting datasets as a whole, it is beneficial to focus on one of archaeology's central concepts: the stratigraphic unit. Here archaeological research broadly follows E. Harris' (1979) approach to capture bodies of sediments - the "stratigraphic units" - as they are encountered during the process of excavation, and how perceivable differences between those bodies can be documented. According to Harris a stratigraphic unit is determined by the identification of its interface and the identification of its chronologically significant limits. Stratigraphic units are characterized by their role in the processes of erosion, sedimentation, weathering and soil formation, as well as by their importance for historical and cultural interpretation. They are used for the contextual study of material remains and as an anchor to

¹ A most recent example discussing the relationship of reflexivity and excavation data can be found in Taylor et al. (2018). In a similar vein projects appreciating "paradata" recognize the intricate details of the excavation process as they take serious what Huggett (2020) called the "silences of knowledge in digital archaeology."

relate archaeological material with an absolute measure of time. Harris emphasizes the importance of interfaces for inferring chronological relationships between stratigraphic units, defined as the smallest perceptible units of soil anterior and posterior to neighboring units. This approach implicitly considers stratigraphic units to be archaeologically isotropic, which implies a uniform cultural and chronological interpretation at every point in their volume, despite their heterogeneous physical composition. Harris implicitly excludes the possibility of archaeologically significant 'continuous' variations that would not be materialized by a contact surface.

Whatever the categories of interpretation used and the level of detail of that interpretation, interpreting the stratigraphic units in historical and cultural terms is an essential condition for developing a synthetic discourse on the evolution of the site, going beyond simple chronology. We agree with B. Desachy (2008) that the question of the cultural and historical significance of the stratigraphic unit must also be asked of the stratigraphic relationship between two units. In fact, a relationship is not simply a type of physical contact (superposition, overlap, etc.) reflecting the process of formation of the terrain, nor is it limited to an element of strict relative chronology (before/after), but also bears witness to a transition from one historical state of the site to another and to the inadequacy of stratigraphic chronology alone to give an account of what can be called the 'cultural lifespan' of stratigraphic units (Carver 1990; Paice 1991).

Although stratigraphy provides a chronological order, the temporal durations represented by the stratigraphic units and their relationships are generally not preserved by stratification, resulting in a loss of temporal information. To estimate this lost chronology, it is necessary to use timing indicators, such as historical data, physicochemical analyses or studying the archaeological material. These indicators must be formalized in the same way as the stratigraphic record if they are to be applied correctly to date stratigraphic units, otherwise erroneous conclusions will be drawn. Despite its importance, the way in which relative stratigraphic chronology is incorporated into absolute chronology remains unclear.

Confronted with this ambiguity, in the following sections we will examine an exemplary approach of modeling the archaeological process in general and stratigraphic information in particular. We will focus on the Archaeological Information Systems (AIS) in use at the site of Bibracte in France. Located on Mount Beuvray (821 m) in the heart of Burgundy (20 km to the west of Autun), Bibracte is considered as the ancient capital of the Aedui people of the first century BC. According to historical sources (e.g. *De Bello Gallico*) Vercingetorix received the command of the Gallic coalition there in the summer of 52 BC, and Julius Caesar might even have completed writing his *De Bello Gallico* here. It is a major archaeological site discovered by Jacques-Gabriel Bulliot in the nineteenth century and it allowed Joseph Déchelette to characterize the oppida as paradigmatic fortified places, typical of the European late Iron Age (Lukas 2014). With the founding of the Centre Archéologique Européen du Mont Beuvray in 1984, Bibracte has become synonymous with the international research program and the Musée de la Civilisation Celtique inaugurated there in 1996.

Bibracte's approach to research data and scientific publications has focused on a documentation management system (bdB) launched in 1996-1997². Initially, the dissemination of results was based on

² While bdB enabled research data to be recorded digitally only within the facilities of the local research center, the actual fieldwork-recording has mostly remained paper-based. Attempts to establish a computer based recording system for digital on site recording were initially undertaken by research teams from partner universities (as early as 1999 - see Fleischer/Schrickel 2004) and most recently on the occasion of the research program Digital Bibracte (Thivet 2019).

traditional research reports and exhaustive publications for completed excavation sectors, which often led to delays in data sharing. To meet the growing demand for immediate access to data, a review of the dissemination process was undertaken from 2012 onwards (Desachy et al. 2012). The aim of this development was to streamline the dissemination process, which led to the creation of “Bibracte Numérique”, a multi-year programme (2018-2021) to promote an integrated approach and collaboration with other archaeological entities³. Since 2017, efforts have been made to systematize dissemination methods, facilitating the ongoing production of archaeological information.

Since the time of bdB’s original implementation, digital advances have considerably transformed the field of archaeology, impacting not only the technical aspects, but also the very nature of the data used in research. With the emergence of new archaeological methods, such as the growing use of geo-referenced data, documentation management systems must constantly evolve to effectively integrate these new elements. bdB features a unique tree-like architecture, designed to capture a multitude of material realities, from excavation sites to samples taken, in line with the archaeological data collection process.

As is the case for many AIS, the above mentioned ambiguities to relate stratigraphic information and absolute chronology, are also apparent in bdB. While stratigraphic relationships which are observed during excavation can be formalized as diagrams, the stages of quantification and the reasoning involved in characterizing the 'cultural life' of stratigraphic units remain practically undocumented here. Yet in contrast to the traditional “stratigraphic unit” as conceptualized by Harris, in bdB archaeological contexts are classified as “excavation unit,” or “unité de fouille” - an attempt to increase the level of processual detail stored with the mere stratigraphical information. This concept, which forms the basis for recording in bdB, allows units to be defined, either as stratigraphic units by recording stratigraphic relationships, or as grouping units based on criteria other than the interfaces identified in the field. This is very useful, for example, for grouping together the same type of material as part of a typological study, or for recording old documentation, such as the data produced by 19th century excavations. While amplifying possible approaches to determine stratigraphically relevant data, also in the case of the “excavation unit” the individual rationales that justify these groupings are only insufficiently explicated and remain circumstantial to the normalized data. In order to incorporate this information with the traditional data regime, the actual processes of encountering, identifying, documenting and interpreting archaeological contexts need to be analyzed and formalized. In that respect progress is being made at Bibracte with the SIAMOIS 2024-2026 project, which aims to develop an open-source Archaeological Information System (AIS) using web technologies and digital humanities practices. Hereby the analysis of the archaeological process is conducted based on a modeling approach developed by Eric Lacombe in his doctoral thesis in information and communication sciences (defended at Bordeaux Montaigne University in 2021). While the original model was intended for the analysis of the digital transformation of networked organizations, and more specifically the potential of dynamic information schematization, here the model enables a more detailed view on the different factors involved in the production of archaeological data.

³ One of the challenges of this program was to support the process of disseminating Bibracte results via the digital services of the Very Large Research Infrastructure (TGIR) Huma-Num (CNRS Joint Service Unit).

T!O

Following Lacombe (2021), the T!O model is directly derived from the logic of energy (“the logic of the included third”) developed by Stephane Lupasco (1951). Lupasco was a French philosopher of Romanian origin (1900 - 1988), inspired by the advances of quantum physics, he defined a logical system, of which classical logic can be considered a particular case. This type of logic is based on the dialectic inherent to energy. Following Lupasco, this logic is not merely reduced to the science of reasoning, but they understand it as a logic of all that exists - allowing for the model to be considered as the logic of the living⁴.

Following Lupasco the classical logic of the excluded third is a binary logic which allows for something to either be the case or not to be the case. Classical logic then is a logic of opposition with an inherent antagonism inside everything that is being asserted. According to the logic of the included third, the antagonism of classical logic is not an appropriate reflection of reality. An antagonism should not be conceived as an either/or-decision, but as a generative force. Something that is stated is then not only opposed to what is not being stated, but that which is being stated is only one possible statement out of the vast array of potential assertions. In that sense, what is being stated - the fact - is actualized in that it is being specified and as having been stated it is also immune to modifications. In consequence, what had been a binary opposition is now described by its position between actualization and potentialization. Actualization and potentialization form an antagonistic pair that opens a spectrum of how we might speak about that fact. Whatever we can say about the fact is in continuous movement and what in the end will be said is contingent on the context of whoever speaks about it. Whoever, whenever, wherever.

By taking the continuous movement of the stated antagonism into account, the spectrum which is opened up, encompasses also all that which has not been said - that which in consequence is called the “included third.” Allowing for the included third to become a constitutive part to what is being said, allows for the emergence of knowledge. Interestingly this will be the case, independent of an assertion or a failed acknowledgement of the included third during the description process. In case we leave it out, it will constitute what we call “implicit” knowledge, and if we care for it, we allow for its investigation in order to better understand how our knowledge has been constituted. Traditional conceptions of knowledge do not consider the implications of the “included third”, following an Aristotelian, binary conception. As discussed above, examples to store archaeological information by inclusion of the included third are rare but do exist: these systems either apply a reflexive method or attempt the storage of so called “paradata”. Potentially whatever can come out of bottom-up approaches like DIY fieldwork documentation systems might also advance the recognition of these furtive data.

⁴ Lupasco’s influence on twentieth-century thought is still little studied. Yet, Joseph Brenner has recently made his work available in English in the book “Logic in reality” (Brenner 2003).

Figure 1 - T!O-model - description logic to represent the transformation of organization

Applying the logic of the “included third” the static antagonism can now be modeled as a dynamism (fig. 1), to become generative as a field of transformation. The model is not constituted by fixed parameters, but assertions are constrained by a set of poles - the attractors (Lacombe 2023). The use of attractors reflects a resolutely relational approach (Deleuze, 1968; Bitbol, 2010). In regards to the discussed antagonism, the two attractors are represented by mathematical operators - the multiplier (\times) and the reducer ($-$). The multiplier creates diversity, variations, dimensions and discontinuity. On the opposing end, the reducer erases the differences, it is a source for continuity. The conjunction of these opposites consists in an integration, represented by a third attractor, the integrator (\int). The relational triangle described here can be called the transformation field.

As shown in Fig.1, the transformation field is in specular opposition to the organization field. Organization is understood as the result of integration, in symmetry to transformation. This field is dynamic as well, translated by the three attractors of the adder ($+$), the separator (\div) and the derivator (∂). In symmetry to the integrator of the Transformation field, the derivator spans open the organization field, with the organizing center oscillating between inner and outer spaces. It is important to note that the model is conceptualized as pan-scalar and can therefore be applied on different levels of organization: an organ, an organism, or a social organization. The analogy with living organisms can help to specify the function of the attractors of the Organization field further: the adder illustrates the organization as being fed by way of the adder, while extracting resources from the environment by way of the separator.

Figure 2 - Information seeds: table to determine the descriptors of organization

In between the two described fields, the information field is opened up (fig.2). It is constituted by a set of elementary units of meaning - the "information seeds." The term "seed" hereby refers to the elementary nature of what the information seed entails. Sticking with the biological analogy, a seed already contains all the potential growth of the plant it derives from and it is about to grow into.

The seeds fall into two categories, descriptors and interpreters. The descriptors are concrete markers that make it possible to describe a situation by crossing two axes, one operational, translated by "who-does-what" evoking the canonical structure of the sentence (subject, verb, complement), the other organizational on 3 levels, "main-context-core" (i.e. "inner-outer-center" or "body-context-heart"), ultimately determining 9 species of descriptors.

On each organizational level descriptors are organized following the same structure and position on the operational axis, resulting in a matrix multiplication allowing to determine the specific configuration of

each information seed. Concerning the “context”, descriptor 4 - which could be transcribed as the “context of the what” - allows for the generation or processing of a set of resources and can be understood as a container for “services.” For instance, if we were to model the concept of “book” and everything that was involved in its production, descriptor 4 would reflect the services provided by the publishing house that publishes several works, the printing house that produces them, the distribution platform that distributes them, the bookstore that sells them or the media library that lends them out, right up to the recycling center that recovers unsold copies. Returning to archaeology, descriptor 4 could be a certain method to be applied during fieldwork.

Following the described logic, the other 8 descriptors can be understood accordingly: Descriptor 5 (or the “context of the does”) groups together a series of events or situations that respond to a common purpose; it designates the project, the program or the mission or - again specifically for archaeology - the excavation project or fieldwork campaign. Descriptor 6 (“context of who”) represents any group of actors, whatever its size, an individual being potentially linked to different groups - the group of researchers bound up within a research project

The “heart level” is part of an internal register: descriptor 7 (“heart of who”) expresses the capacity, the potential of the actor or the group, attached to their role or mission and translating a competence. An excavator in an archaeological project would find their specific role determined here. Descriptor 8 (“heart of does”) designates the action, an elementary temporal unit, knowing that only the actions that are significant for the discourse are memorized. Again translated to the field of archaeology, the actual application of a chosen method is expressed with an action - the taking of a sample or the extraction of a quantity of soil from a designated archaeological unit. Descriptor 9 (“heart of what”) at last represents the idea, the objective, the intention, translating a reason for being, or in archaeological terms a research goal.

In addition to these 9 species of descriptors, there is the interpreter, 0 the “concept”, an abstraction designating a category, a theme or a keyword. The 10 seeds are identified by the same reduced set of attributes, in particular contextualization attributes, such as domain, author, space or time, which are therefore not represented by seeds. The order of description is left free, the attributes remain optional. By analogy with the seed in botany, an information seed is a concentrate. It develops by putting it into relationships, thus forming a multidimensional structure, a graph called a schema, comparable to a rhizome. If seeds are formally defined as reifications of relationships between the 3 transformation attractors, and the 3 organizational attractors, they are themselves linked by 6 types of relationship, describing either transformational or organizational processes. The three transformational relations are correlation, formation (i.e. causality) and conjunction, whereby the correlation is the default relation which is at the basis of any more complex relationality that can be established. A change of objective is thus expressed by two seeds “9” linked by causality, the end date of the first corresponding to the start date of the second. The three organizational relations are appropriation - in the sense of acquiring extracted resources to respond to a need for an energetic imbalance (“unity makes strength”), domination - in the sense of mastering life or achievement (“divide and conquer”), and opposition. As mentioned above, by default information seeds are linked by mere correlation – the fact that there is a relationship and that relationship has a scientific value. With increasing depth of investigation of the excavation process, a certain directionality between the seeds becomes apparent. This directionality could either mean a direction of transformation, or at the same time a type causality between the seeds in question. The third relationship of the “tuner of the organization” is less tangible, but it is the

relationship responsible for the emergence of knowledge because it signifies the informational effect of the interaction of seeds.

The model as it has been described so far, has been introduced at the Centre Archeologique Europeen du Mont Beuvray, a research center with the scope to conduct research at the late Iron Age oppidum Bibracte. Allow its members to model their organization, they were able to discuss and develop the constitutional processes in use at Bibracte in order to identify processes that work well and others that are in need of improvement.

T!O and bdB

Within SIAMOIS modeling the process of an archaeological excavation with T!O assists the identification of necessary aspects of recording and identifying shared as well as disparate conceptualizations at the partner institutions. In the following section T!O is applied to model the processes of excavation and typological analysis in order to show how modeling these processes can help understanding the requirements as well as conceptual divergences in archaeological discourses on the fundamental level of data recording.

Modeling the excavation process

The process of an archaeological excavation as modeled with T!O is illustrated in 6 steps, with figures from 3A to 3F.

Figure 3A 3B - The process of an archaeological excavation as modeled with T!O (part 1).

In a first step (fig.3A) the information seeds for actor (1) and encounter (2) are situated on the axis for the internal space. In order to model an actor who relates themselves to encounter something like an archaeological context, the actor is transformed from their being related to

In a second step (fig.3B) the encounter happens on the spatial axis, but an activity involving the archaeological context requires a transformation from the unique attractor to the multiple attractor. Again in other words, the actor extends themselves onto the location of the

the unique attractor, towards being related to the organizational attractor. In other words, the individual actor engages towards an activity which is integrated with the organization. The relations activated here are that of correlation - the relation that is active by default - and the transformation.

archaeological context. Besides correlation and transformation we recognize the relation of appropriation as the encounter enables the actor to move onto the resource. Throughout this transformation and taking into consideration the dynamics of continuous movement between actualization and potentialization underlying all processes, the actor continuously examines their relationality with the context and themselves - in fact an expression of reflexivity during that process. The encounter in which the actor is involved translates (original meaning of "translatio") them towards actualization.

Figure 3C 3D - The process of an archaeological excavation as modeled with T!O (part 2).

A third step (fig.3C) models the actor's activity predetermined by them being part of a research project from which they derive their specific role (information seed 7). Therefore the actor is organized in a determined space and they are transformed by adopting a causal directionality, which gives them their role on site. The primary relationships in this situation are transformation and conjunction so that acting following that role, the actor becomes their role. Framed by that role they can make decisions and decide on how that directionality becomes manifest.

In the next step (fig.3D) the actor's relation with the context following a certain role moreover implies following general directives defined by the project. These constraints are modeled as an actor fulfilling their role to become instrumental for the progress of the excavation. The primary relation being transformation, the organized is transformed from an integrated being towards expansion specifying the actual interaction with the archaeological context. In other words, the potential excavator is being actualized by way of their objective.

Figure 3E 3F - The process of an archaeological excavation as modeled with T!O (part 3).

At the same time (fig.3E), the general directives are prone to being modified in regard to specific circumstances. The dynamism is expressed by issuing specific tasks or staying with the model, transforming from being related to a multiple attractor towards being integrated. The general role finds its necessary configuration for the task at hand and the overall excavation strategy becomes manifest.

Finally (fig.3F) the excavator equipped with a role, directives and an outline for their task is enabled to move into the archaeological context and begins digging. Thereby the organizational aspects of the directive are transformed towards a spatial contraction and the resource identified during the initial encounter is now actualized by the actors intention. The relationship with the resource is thereby that of transformation but also predation, as the context is being processed and extracted. As we can see, the resulting model allows for reflecting on the complex interaction of the excavator with their context, taking into account the different levels of organizational rules embedded in general strategies, directives and definition of tasks.

Already modeling this basic and partial aspect of the archaeological process with T!O shows a set of aspects that are for now ignored within bdB. First, the transformation from seeds 2 to 3 (encounter towards resource) shows that the actor never escapes their environmental context, which makes it necessary to examine these parameters continuously and document the effects of the process. Secondly, the movement from seeds 1 to 7 is practically expressed by the actors making decisions, again an important element to be documented in order to understand the data resulting from that process.

On a general level, the model shows as well that the actor's presence with their context is only complete by taking into account the temporal aspects of the same activity. In consequence an

information system treating excavation data necessitates the recording of the temporal structure of these activities.

Regarding the ambiguities of the concept of “stratigraphic unit”, the model underscores the increased attention to alternative ways of grouping archaeological data, similar to those enabled by the use of the “excavation unit.” Allowing for a differential documentation depending on whether a unit is a traditional stratigraphic unit, a unit of grouped material in view of the facilitation of typological studies or even the attribution of historical excavation units established in the 19th century, the “excavation unit” is a more appropriate reflection of actual excavation processes. Breaking this process down with T!O now moreover allows for the identification of moments within the process, where information should be gathered in order to enable a more detailed recording of the reasoning process involved in the definition of such a unit. Each movement on the network of information seeds holds potential data in that respect. The proposed model therefore allows for reflecting on institutional processes at the same time as it indicates the necessary parameters to organize and record.

Modeling archaeological reasoning

Modeling the process of soil extraction obviously reflects only a small part of the archaeological process. As discussed above, large parts of the archaeological discourse are recorded in vernacular language, which are fluid but disconnected from the data. In order to expand the present example accordingly, modeling the process of confronting excavated objects with research documents will shed light on the requirements to digitally encode both discourse and data to enable their connection (interoperability), ultimately allowing them to delegate to machines some of their memory and processing capabilities (sorting and calculation).

Figure 3G 3H - The implications of archaeological typologies for the archaeological processes as modeled with T!O.

In archaeology it is quite common for a vocabulary to be specifically created or authoritative set of rules issued by the related

reorganized based on a particular case study and for the same term to refer to different, evolving realities depending on the context (cultural, chronological, etc.) and viewpoints, without specialists always being aware of it. Therefore the process of extracting an object is further modeled by its confrontation with a typology (fig.3G).

research community, but the retrieved objects have initially formed the basis for the creation of the very typology and throughout the prolonged interaction on site, the authoritative document is transformed as well. As a term used as a keyword in a catalog or a database may not necessarily refer to the same material or conceptual realities according to its users. In consequence, this issue of polysemy affects documentation management, and even casts doubt on the comparison of archaeological corpora since the meaning of vocabularies used to index data often varies from one dataset (database or publications) to another.

The polysemy apparent in the example is typically clarified in scientific publications by referencing the bibliographical information that includes the producer's surname and the year of term creation – what we refer to as the "vintage." This reliance on the vintage has emerged as an obvious and functional solution in the presentation of competing and contextualized controlled vocabularies by appending a bibliographic citation call to the term label: name(s) + year. Stemming from this choice, the understanding of a term is embedded within the same vintaged bibliographic context.

Acknowledging the situation of polysemy of terms and its resolution merely outside of the recording system by way of traditional publications, the Bibracte project conducted an experiment as part of the publication "La vaisselle céramique de Bibracte" (Barrier/Luginbühl 2021). In parallel to it being published as a traditional book, the specialized vocabulary used to characterize and describe pottery fragments was furthermore published by using the thesaurus manager Opentheso (<https://opentheso.huma-num.fr/opentheso/>). Opentheso is compliant with the ISO 25964 standard (<https://www.iso.org/en/standard/53657.html>) that guides the development of controlled vocabularies (Durost et al. 2022). One of the rules of the standard establishes the impossibility of presenting two strictly identical terms in the same thesaurus while associating them with different semantic spaces (position in the hierarchy of terms, relationships, definition).

The definition (in the sense of the ISO 1087-2019 standard: "representation of a concept by an expression that describes it and differentiates it from related concepts") serves to individualize the concept by qualifying its properties. It specifies the researcher's paradigm for comprehending their subject of study, which, through the alignment of terms from different thesauri, can be confronted with the multiplicity of viewpoints presented therein and thus become part of a knowledge network. Furthermore, for a given type of artifact, the methods of study and analysis can change depending on the research question, the researcher's perspective, and taphonomic conditions (i.e., all the physico-chemical processes that occur after the object is abandoned). In case objects of an unknown type are retrieved, the typology requires modification. In our example the discovery of a lid (and the recipient covered by it) are from now on to be considered as a potential object not merely from a settlement context but also as a funerary object. While the process is obviously known and a common event in archaeology, the actualization process of modifying the typology is rarely recorded with information

systems in use. Even less the means of modification of authoritative rules by way of which retrieved objects were used in order to modify the typology.

Consequently and as a further issue for internal interoperability, the archaeologist creates their own vocabulary and/or draws part or all of their terminology from a reference already used elsewhere, adapting it to meet their needs. To accurately understand the vocabularies created or invoked by authors, it is necessary to have access to the corpus(es) upon which they are based. Connecting them for comparisons is a fundamental need, which in the digital age is expressed as the requirement for a technological networking of knowledge. A thesaurus manager is entirely capable of initiating this through its internal relationships (associations between concepts within the same thesaurus) and external relationships (alignments between concepts from different thesauri), as long as the organization and networking of these vocabularies are extended by access to the data recorded and/or defined based on material or immaterial realities. Indeed, only by returning to the data can one appreciate the meaning of the vocabulary and the relevance of alignments with a comparative vocabulary, and therefore, its associated dataset.

In conclusion it is necessary to formalize the vocabularies used for data description by a researcher, that is, to expose the uniqueness of their perspective and the richness of their vocabulary, to be capable of understanding other paradigms, and to be able to compare their terminology within the semantic space of their colleagues.

Conclusion

The narration of a site's history involves arranging the collected data, which includes information derived from the data and their relationships, as well as the nature of the reasoning to achieve this, while maintaining a constant concern to be tested against archaeological facts. Currently, this work is carried out through the institutionalized dissemination of written publications, such as scientific reports, articles, or monographs, in vernacular language. Whether recording processes are established in collaboration or by way of retrotheorization, it is necessary to describe these processes systematically. T!O allows for the investigation of archaeological processes in order to identify the necessary questions to be answered when attempting to define a projected knowledge structure. The questions (and answers) are both distinctive of the specific group of researchers while at the same time underscoring commonalities with other groups or the discipline in general. In the long run this approach allows for the assessment of potential mappings with already existing ontologies, thereby bridging not only internal but also external interoperabilities.

Updates in archaeological discourse are part of a permanent iterative process (Moberg 1969), oscillating (feedback) between the stages of archaeography (requesting / observing [archaeometry, archaeoscopy] / describing [ordering, classifying, sorting, generalizing]) and those of producing discourse about the past (archaeology: Ἀρχαῖος, "ancient", and Λόγος, "discourse") proper (analyzing, associating, interpreting, understanding, etc.). However, such a heuristic framework is hindered by a highly incomplete restitution of information. This methodological weakness has early on caught the attention of the French archaeological community (Gardin 1971; Tchernia et al. 1984).

Current digital technologies have undoubtedly reached the necessary maturity to address this techno-methodological question, but as it stands, this would constrain the archaeological community to

condition its heuristic practice to the use of tools conceptualized outside its intellectual realm, which is not desirable for epistemological (their logic would elude it) and practical reasons (it wouldn't master them). Nevertheless, these digital solutions could reduce the excessive reliance on cumulative deductive abilities derived from each individual's experience and the common culture of the discipline, which places too much emphasis on the implicit and individual memorization capacity. How can the transition be made, in collaboration with archaeologists (co-construction), from restitutions in vernacular language, fluid but disconnected from the data, to digital encodings faithful to both discourse and data, allowing them to be connected (interoperability), and ultimately enabling them to delegate to machines a portion of their memorization and processing capabilities (classification and calculation)?

It would be appropriate to envisage a new system that would encourage and network both the diversity of the data and the accepted plurality of points of view. If ontologies are ideal candidates to map the common aspects of a recordings system, either in regards to the internal or external interoperability, what is then the best approach to develop the overall system by tolerating conceptual differences as well as retaining the potential for later integration with external databases? As we have seen, most AIS are far from being conceptualized in a collaborative fashion and also retrotheorization of existing systems is mostly left to a small group attempting to reproduce theoretical deliberations that were supposedly occurring during the development of an AIS. To address this limitation, a new system fostering diversity of data and viewpoints is necessary. This would enable a more comprehensive and collaborative synthesis of archaeological paradigms.

In emphasis to the above mentioned difficulties to trace individual treatments of the archaeological context, this modeling approach takes seriously the fact that already AIS can be considered as shared conceptualizations in the sense of a group of researchers buying into their institutions' chosen organization of knowledge.

T!O proposes a paradigm shift that goes beyond binary logic and invites us to consider ontologies from a dynamic point of view: invariants are limited to operations, not states. This approach has two major advantages: on the one hand, it is compatible with the living world, and on the other, it harmonizes the understanding of phenomena currently dealt with in different disciplines, after translating specific terms into the T!O language. From a practical point of view, as the model is recent, it does not yet have specific tools to facilitate its deployment. However, this disadvantage is offset by the fact that it can be gradually implemented in existing information systems. In this way, SIAMOIS ultimately hopes to meet the primary requirement of ontologies as discussed by Gruber, thereby developing a genuine 'shared conceptualization' of archaeological research.

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Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

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